

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“THE LONGEST TEARS”

Here it goes again.

When I do not know where I'm supposed to position myself.

Where i am put into a loop of not knowing
and wasting my heart and mind.

Where I am constantly blinded and left to stay put
And only called when needed.

How come I struggle to get myself out?
How come I am being push and pull to nowhere?

How come it feels like I'm the one begging for love?
How did I become this empty?

How come I made my self so little to some who cannot appreciate me?
How come I keep myself being disrespected?

How come I keep on overlooking the manipulation??
How can you do this to the one you love??

How can you keep up the lies?
How can bare minimum even dies?

How can tears not stop when the eyes are dry?
Days, weeks, months passed by.

The eyes are dry but the heart in tears,
The longest tears please come oh come to end, I can't bear.